

SERGEI YESENIN: DRAMATIC POEM "PUGACHEV"
СЕРГЕЙ ЕСЕНИН: ДРАМАТИЧЕСКАЯ ПОЭМА «ПУГАЧЕВ»

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Abstract: The Pugachev uprising left a significant mark in Russian history. True, many specialists give him completely ambiguous assessments. Let's consider the topic "S. Yesenin, "Pugachev": a short summary "and let's pay attention to how the events of that time are watched by the great poet. The work, by the way, supports the idea of a "good king"

Keywords: History, literature, work, different peoples, theme and idea, composition.

Yesenin was extremely thorough in the collection of materials before writing the poem "Pugachev". The poet decided to cover one of the most difficult stages in the development of national history, wanted to tell about that time as truthfully as possible. All the necessary historical information he collected and researched for several years. The poet began work on the poem in 1921, and in 1922 it was already published as a separate book.

Yesenin himself spoke about his work on the work to I. N. Rozanov. It is worth noting that Sergei Yesenin's favorite poet was Pushkin, but to the coverage of this rebellion in the works of the great poet Yesenin was critical. The author of the poem "Pugachev" in the study of historical facts came to the conclusion that, unfortunately, in the texts of Pushkin much has been distorted. In Pushkin's works there are very few names of the rebels, but there are many people who suffered at the hands of the

Pugachevites, the tampers of the rebellion. Yesenin notes that he has tried to depict not only Pugachev, but also to recreate a bright and objective images of his associates. In addition, Sergei Yesenin in his poem seeks to add dynamism to the action, changing the characters in each scene. No one is repeated except Pugachev himself. This technique creates an emphasis on his image as well.

It is interesting that it was Khlopusha's monologue that was often read by Yesenin himself, even a phonogram of the recording survives.

Composition, plot, rhyme and rhythm

The poem "Pugachev" consists of eight parts. In them a picture of the peasant uprising unfolds sequentially. First, Pugachev appears in Yaitsk town. There he talks to the watchman and understands that he must be the man who "first throws the stone." The flight of the Kalmyks is then described. Then, on an autumn night, Pugachev discusses the rebellion with Karavaev. In the next part, readers already learn of Pugachev's intention to call himself Peter. He wants to unite the different peoples in rebellion and hopes to succeed.

Khlopusha appears before the readers in the chapter "The Ural Convict." The hero notes that Pugachev is loved for his prowess and riotousness; it makes little difference to him whether the rebel is actually Peter. The rebels move toward the cities, but the revolt is suppressed. Pugachev is surrounded by Cossacks. He has failed to hold power in his hands, unable to change the destined course of history. He is alone again, without his comrades-in-arms, as in the very beginning of the poem, which creates a kind of circular composition.

The poem is written in the tradition of the original literary movement. Here readers immediately see that Yesenin is a representative of Imagism. This is evident from the first lines: "The road rumbles into an eerie space," "The moon, like a yellow bear, in the wet grass crawls." Rhyme and rhythm and size are constantly changing here, so it is difficult to label everything with a single name. At the same time, the overall rhythm is clearly visible, Yesenin's syllable is very light.

Theme and idea

In the poem "Pugachev" the rebels appear as brave, courageous people. They are confident in their rightness, ready to die to achieve the goal. Pugachev's companions are convinced: it is necessary to change the existing order. They are able to use different methods and means, not afraid of battle. Of course, the main theme of the work was the peasant uprising. It demonstrated to the full extent of prowess, fearlessness of the people.

It can be noted that from the very beginning it is easy to predict that the uprising is doomed. Yesenin well conveys the general atmosphere, in which it is almost impossible to imagine a happy outcome of the rebellion.

Artistic means

In the poem "Pugachev" Sergei Yesenin makes extensive use of symbols and allegories, comparisons, fanciful images, characteristic of Imagism.

Here are a few examples: "the toad eyes of the village," heads "jumping from their shoulders with yellow cats," "in the chest, like in a den, the warm soul of a beast is stirring," "eyes, like two chain dogs, are stirring in the salty moisture." Yesenin also frequently uses threefold repetition, which is particularly poignant at the end of the poem. At the beginning of the part "The end of Pugachev" the hero asks: "You have gone mad! You have gone mad! You are mad!" Near the very end he says, "What happened? What happened? What happened?" The closed nature of the plot, the inevitability of the collapse of the rebellion are vividly evident in these refrains.

In his famous poem "Pugachev" Sergey Yesenin portrays the peasant uprising with respect, sympathy and sympathy, draws the image of a historical figure - Yemelyan Pugachev. Now we can look at the bloody uprising differently, but in the poet's work the readers can clearly see the uniqueness of characters, strength of spirit and prowess of people. Even with such extraordinary images, means of imagery, the poem reads easily, which provides an airy syllable of Sergei Yesenin.

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